

PATENT SUMMARY

CONTRAST AGENTS FOR MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING (MRI) AND THEIR USE

Patent	WO-2019012530-A1
Inventor	BERLIN SHAI (IL)
Assignee	TECHNION RES & DEV FOUNDATION (IL)
Date	Priority 2017/07/10

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1 Abstract

The invention relates to a hybrid molecule comprising at least one contrast agent, and at least one substrate of a self-labeling enzyme, and optionally a fluorescent moiety. The invention also relates to compositions comprising said hybrid molecule and their use.

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2 Full Text

PATENTSCOPE

<https://patentscope.wipo.int/search/en/detail.jsf?docId=WO2019012530>

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3 Important Dates

3.1 Priority Date

2017/07/10

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3.2 Filing Date

2018/07/10

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3.3 Publication Date

2019/01/17

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6 Linked Chemicals

6.1 PubChem Compounds

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6.2 PubChem Substances

▶ PubChem

7 Linked Proteins

▶ PubChem

8 Linked Genes

▶ PubChem

9 Linked Taxonomies

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10 Patent Family

[EP-3651808-A1](#)
[EP-3651808-A4](#)
[US-2020405885-A1](#)
[WO-2019012530-A1](#)

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11 Classification

11.1 IPC

A61K49/10 (inventive, first)

A61B5/055 (inventive)

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11.2 CPC

A61K49/0052 (inventive)

A61K49/0002 (inventive, first)

A61K49/0041 (inventive)

A61K49/106 (inventive)

A61K49/0045 (inventive)

A61K49/04 (inventive)

A61K49/14 (inventive)

A61K49/108 (inventive)

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A61K49/0002 (inventive, first)

A61K48/00

A61K49/0041 (inventive)

A61K49/0052 (inventive)

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12 Citations

[US-2013302258-A1](#) (XY) (ISR)

CHEN, Z. ET AL.: "Chemical tags: inspiration for advanced imaging techniques", CURRENT OPINION IN CHEMICAL BIOLOGY, vol. 17, no. 4, 12 June 2013 (2013-06-12), pages 637 - 643, XP055569883, Retrieved from the Internet <URL:http://www.columbia.edu/cu/chemistry/groups/min/pdf/15-chemical%20tags.pdf> (A) (ISR)

LUKINAVIČIUS, G. ET AL.: "A near-infrared fluorophore for live- cell super-resolution microscopy of cellular proteins", NATURE CHEMISTRY, vol. 5, no. 2, 6 January 2013 (2013-01-06), pages 132 - 139, XP008169702, Retrieved from the Internet <URL:https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Grazvydas_Lukinavicius/publication/235367078_A_near-infrared_fluorophore_for_live-cell_super-resolution_microscopy_of_cellular_proteins/links/542927270cf26120b7b59dec/A-near-infrared-fluorophore-for-live-cell-super-resolution-microscopy-of-cellular-protein> (Y) (ISR)

See also references of EP 3651808A4 (ISR)

STRAUCH, R. C. ET AL.: "Reporter protein-targeted probes for magnetic resonance imaging", JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN CHEMICAL SOCIETY, vol. 133, no. 41, 19 October 2011 (2011-10-19), pages 16346 - 16349, XP055569878, Retrieved from the Internet <URL:https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/ja206134b> (X) (ISR)

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13 Similar Patents

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[JP-2011111456-A](#)
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[US-2020405885-A1](#)
[JP-5968343-B2](#)
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[KR-20200135224-A](#)
[EP-1209469-A1](#)

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14 Information Sources

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